

Proposal of a new design of central solar receiver for pressurised gases and supercritical fluids

M.J. Montes^{a,b,*}, R. Guédez^c, D. D'Souza^{a,b}, J.I. Linares^d, J. González-Aguilar^b, M. Romero^b

^a E.T.S. Ingenieros Industriales - UNED, C/Juan Del Rosal 12, 28040, Madrid, Spain

^b High Temperature Processes Unit, IMDEA Energy, Avda. Ramón de La Sagra 3, 28935, Móstoles, Spain

^c Department of Energy Technology, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Brinellvägen 68, 100 44, Stockholm, Sweden

^d Comillas Pontifical University, Alberto Aguilera, 25, 28015, Madrid, Spain

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ABSTRACT

This work presents a novel design of microchannel central receiver for pressurised gases and supercritical fluids in solar tower plants. It consists of a radial arrangement of vertical absorber panels that converge on the central axis of the tower. The absorber panels comprise compact structures, whose compactness is increased in one flow pass compared to the previous one, as the fluid is heated. This concept reduces radiation heat losses due to its light-trapping geometry and increases heat transfer to the thermal fluid without over penalising its pressure drop.

For the receiver assessment, it has been developed a thermal resistance model characterising the fluid heating along the panel height and the temperature gradient between parallel channel rows of the compact structure across the panel thickness. Once the thermal and optical boundary conditions are defined, an optimisation analysis of the main geometrical parameters of the receiver has been accomplished. The receiver performance is evaluated by means of a global exergy efficiency referred to the solar subsystem, which computes the receiver heat losses, the fluid pressure drop and the optical efficiency of the heliostat field in which the receiver is integrated. For each parametric optimisation, the configuration that maximises this efficiency is identified.

1. Introduction

The Gen3 programme for Solar Thermal Power Plants (STPPs) identifies three concentrating solar receiver technologies, all coupled to a supercritical CO₂ (sCO₂) power cycle, and whose common objective is to increase the overall efficiency while reducing the electricity generation cost. Each of these technologies is characterised by the type of thermal carrier used in the receiver; namely, molten salts, falling particles or gas-phase fluids [1].

Gas-phase fluid receivers are characterised by reliable operation at high temperature, although fluid thermophysical properties result in poor heat transfer. A fluid flow channel design with intrinsically improved heat transfer is the microchannel receiver [2]. Its compact structure increases the heat transfer area for the same receiver volume and improves the convective heat transfer coefficient due to the smaller diffusion length as compared to conventional tubes [3–5]. As result, temperature difference between the external receiver surface and the fluid as well as heat losses from the receiver to the environment for the same target fluid temperature are reduced. Besides, the microchannel

receiver concept is favoured if the gas is pressurised. This is because gas density is roughly proportional to the pressure; thus, fluid velocity is much lower at high pressure than at low pressure. As gas viscosity does not vary much with pressure; the above characteristics mean that pressure drop in gases is reduced at lower velocities [5].

The state-of-art during the last decade of microchannel receivers for pressurised gases and supercritical fluids begins with the review of Compact Heat Exchanger (CHE) structures applied to solar receivers from Li et al. [2]. According to this work, Plate Heat Exchanger (PHE), Plate-Fin Heat Exchanger (PFHE), Printed Circuit Heat Exchanger (PCHE) and ceramic heat exchanger designs may meet the requirements for a new generation of solar receivers. Among them, diffusion bonded heat exchangers (such as PFHE, PCHE) would be suitable for pressurised receivers, as they can operate at elevated pressures and temperatures. In a later work, the same authors presented the thermal model and experimental set-up of a prototype microchannel receiver [5]. From there, several simulation models, reviews and prototypes can be highlighted [6,7]. Among the reported designs, the two most relevant to the design presented in this paper are briefly described as follows. The first one was a 3 MW_{th} microchannel receiver presented by Besarati et al. [8];

* Corresponding author. E.T.S. Ingenieros Industriales - UNED, C/Juan del Rosal 12, 28040, Madrid, Spain.

E-mail address: mjmontes@ind.uned.es (M.J. Montes).

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Acronyms		Greek Letters	
AR	Aspect Ratio	\dot{Q}	Thermal power (W)
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics	R	Thermal resistance (K W ⁻¹)
CHE	Compact Heat Exchanger		Ideal gas constant (J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
HCE	Heat Control Element	Re	Reynolds number
HTD	Heat Transfer Degradation	T	Temperature (K)
HTF	Heat Transfer Fluid	t	Thickness (m)
HX	Heat Exchanger	u	Velocity (m s ⁻¹)
NREL	National Renewable Energy Laboratory	W	Width (m)
PCHE	Printed Circuit Heat Exchanger, PFHE Plate Fin Heat Exchanger	\dot{W}	Electrical power (W)
PHE	Plate Heat Exchanger	δ	Half-angle of the cone subtended by the sun's disc
STAR	Solar Thermal Advanced Receiver	ε	Emissivity
STPP	Solar Thermal Power Plant	η	Efficiency
TRM	Thermal Resistance Model	ρ	Density (kg m ⁻³)
		σ	Stefan-Boltzmann constant
<i>Notation. Latin letters</i>		<i>Subscripts</i>	
A	Área (m ²)	amb	Ambient
c _p	Specific heat (J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	c	Channel
D _h	Hydraulic diameter	cond	Conduction
F	View factor	conv	Convection
f	Darcy/Fanning pressure friction loss factor	f	fin
h	Specific enthalpy (J kg ⁻¹)	HCE	Heat collector element
h _{conv}	Convection heat transfer coefficient (W m ⁻² K ⁻¹)	HTF	Heat transfer fluid
k	Thermal conductivity (W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	loss	Heat loss
L	Length (m)	p	Pressure, plate
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate (kg s ⁻¹)	r	Infrared (super-index)
N	Number of channels	rad	Radiation
ΔP	Pressure drop (Pa)	rec	Receiver
P	Pressure (Pa)	ref	Reflection
Pr	Prandtl number	s	Solar (super-index)
		th	Thermal

the absorber panels consisted of a PFHE structure with a plain rectangular fin core. Its optimal geometry was obtained according to an optimisation process, which is explained in the same article. The second design was developed by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) [9]. It consisted of a 2 MW_e microchannel receiver, whose absorber panels had a compact structure consisting of a single row of wavy fin with two plates attached to this core by diffusion. The absorber panels were arranged in a cavity and the plates acted as absorbers. Sullivan et al. [9] also reported the design and simulation of a 10 MW_e receiver based on this concept. Here, the absorber panels were arranged to form an external cylindrical receiver. In the two previous receiver designs, it was shown that absorber panels based on a microchannel structure can be arranged either as a cavity or as an external receiver. As in these two previous designs, when the operating temperature is high, the cavity receiver is preferred because it leads to lower heat losses [10]. However, there are current designs that minimise radiation loss from the outer surface of external receivers, known as light-trapping geometries [11–13], for example, the arrangement of small quartz tubes attached perpendicularly to the primary surface exposed to radiation in the NREL prototype [9]. It should be noted that in all previously described prototypes, the absorber panels are radiated on only one of their two sides, the opposite side being insulated to minimise thermal losses (adiabatic wall).

This work proposes an original microchannel receiver design for pressurised gases and supercritical fluids, which applies the radial configuration to absorber panels consisted of compact structures of increasing compactness [14], depicted in Fig. 1. In the design proposed, the bladed receiver concept [15–17] is applied, so the vertical absorber panels converge on the axis of the tower, and the concentrated solar radiation falls upon both sides of the absorber panel, as shown in Fig. 1.

This configuration is known as STAR (Solar Thermal Advanced Receiver) design, and it has been already proposed in absorber panels composed of tubes [18–20]; in that case, the panel may suffer deformation and bending at high radiation fluxes due to the tube wall is very thin. The novelty of this proposal is applying the STAR configuration to absorber panels formed by compact structures. This feature overcomes one of the main drawbacks of microchannel receiver concepts, that is the high thermal gradient through the absorber panel thickness due to the low thermal conductivity of standard materials currently used in these structures, such as stainless steel, nickel and even titanium alloys [2,21]. Besides, all previous designs proposed to date consider a uniform compactness along the entire fluid circulation path, i.e. the channels have a fixed cross-section. As seen in Fig. 1, each fluid pass has a channel with a constant hydraulic diameter and this one decreases from one pass to the next in the fluid direction.

This work addresses the analysis and geometrical optimisation of this original microchannel receiver design. To achieve this objective, this manuscript is organised as follow. Firstly, there is a preliminary section in which the new receiver concept is explained, highlighting its main features. After that, the methodology section introduces the two-dimensional heat transfer model characterising the receiver, and the simulation algorithm; then, the boundary conditions of the receiver, both optical and thermal are established; finally, the most representative geometrical parameters of the microchannel receiver are identified; these parameters are optimised in order to maximise the objective function, in this case, the global exergy efficiency referred to the solar subsystem. The results section presents the outcomes of two representative optimisation analyses. The first one focus on the radial configuration, and it examines the effect of increasing the number of panels. The second one concerns one absorber panel, and it studies the effect of

Fig. 1. Scheme of the microchannel central solar receiver analysed in this work.

increasing compactness. At the end, there is a section about conclusions and future works.

2. The microchannel receiver consisting of absorber panels of increasing compactness in radial arrangement

This section compares the radial receiver of increasing compactness with a conventional external receiver, to highlight the advantages of the proposed new concept. Specifically, both receivers are considered to have six absorber panels of the same dimensions (height, width and thickness) and the same external tower diameter, as shown in Fig. 2, in which each absorber panel is connected in parallel. It is obvious that the receivers to be compared do not have the same thermal performance. This section is only intended to qualitatively show what would be the advantages of the novel design presented: a microchannel receiver consisted of absorber panels of gradual compactness, and in radial configuration.

As depicted in Fig. 2, the fluid flow modes are different for the two receivers, although this will not be used in the comparison. In the external receiver, the fluid circulates vertically through the panel in a single flow pass, while in the radial receiver, the fluid circulates vertically through the panel in two flow passes. The fluid enters the panel near the tower diameter, and it circulates vertically from the bottom to the top; then, it reverses direction and it goes from the top to the bottom of the panel, exiting near the tower axis. In this way, the fluid at lower temperature is in contact with the least irradiated area of the panel, while the fluid at higher temperature is in contact with the most irradiated area of the panel, reducing the exergy loss associated with the overall heat transfer.

Regarding the radial arrangement of the absorber panels, three clear advantages can be identified if the receiver is intended for the thermal application described in this paper. Firstly, heat losses are reduced, as the view factor from the panel side to the atmosphere is less than the unity due to the cavity effect, compared to a conventional external receiver, in which this same view factor is equal to the unity. The second advantage is that the irradiated surface of the receiver is larger than that of a conventional external receiver, which makes it possible, for the same receiver volume (diameter and height), to heat a greater mass flow

Fig. 2. Top view cross section of analysed solar receivers. (a) External receiver with six absorber panels; and (b) Microchannel receiver with six absorber panels of increasing compactness in radial arrangement.

within the same temperature increment, thus increasing the thermal power. Particularly, for the examples shown in Fig. 2, the exposed absorber area in the radial receiver is twice that of the external receiver, if the panel width and height are the same for both receivers. The third benefit, which is linked to this last characteristic, is a lower thermal resistance through the panel thickness compared to a panel of the same thickness since the absorber panel in the radial configuration is irradiated on both sides, while it is only one side exposed to solar radiation in an external receiver. It is important to note that the number of panels is not limited to six. The radial receiver can consist of more panels, provided that they are equally distributed, keeping the same convergence angle.

The increasing compactness within each absorber panel allows to modify and optimise fluid heat transfer to the boundary conditions. According to Hesselgreaves [22], the hydraulic diameter D_h of the channel is the main parameter that characterises compactness. Accordingly, a reduced hydraulic diameter causes higher Reynolds numbers, which means higher turbulence and better heat transfer. However, higher velocity leads to higher pressure drop, then a receiver geometry optimisation is required by to maximising the exergy efficiency. To perform this parametric optimisation, a two-dimensional

Fig. 3. Thermal resistance circuit to model the heat transfer in the compact structure of the absorber panel.

Fig. 4. Layout of the recompression sCO₂ cycle with solar thermal power supply through the low-pressure side (Source: [34]). T, Turbine; G, Generator; MC, Main Compressor; AC, Auxiliary Compressor; LTR, Low Temperature Recuperator; HTR, High Temperature Recuperator; and PC, pre-cooled.

model of the proposed microchannel receiver has been used, because of its simplicity and versatility.

3. Methodology

3.1. Thermo-fluid dynamic model of the microchannel receiver

The thermal model described below is similar the one developed for conventional external microchannel receivers by D'Souza et al. [23]. This paper contains a detailed description of the model, so only the main equations and the iterative process will be addressed in this work. The two-dimensional model is based on thermal resistances and is applied to a single panel.

The thermal model first characterises the fluid heating of the pressurised gas or supercritical fluid along the flow direction. For the

calculation of the thermal losses, it is necessary to obtain the temperature of the outer wall of the absorber panel, for which an additional thermal model is introduced that determines the heat transfer through the thickness of the panel, consisting of a finned core with multiple parallel rows. Both models have been implemented in Matlab [24] and they are explained below.

The first thermal model calculates the fluid heating along the panel height, this is discretised in many equally long elements (named Heat Control Elements, HCEs) in the flow direction. For each HCE, it is assumed that the heat flux is constant and normal to its surface, and the fluid properties are also constant and equal to the arithmetic mean between the element inlet and outlet [25]. Concentrated solar radiation falling upon on the outer panel wall (\dot{Q}_{solar}) is split in absorbed (\dot{Q}_{abs}) and reflected ($\dot{Q}_{loss,ref}$) contributions. The absorbed radiation is transmitted by conduction through the walls of the compact structure ($\dot{Q}_{cond,wall}$) and finally transmitted by convection to the fluid ($\dot{Q}_{conv,HTF}$). Because the temperature of the outer wall of the absorber panel is higher than the ambient temperature, there are heat losses by convection ($\dot{Q}_{loss,conv}$) and radiation ($\dot{Q}_{loss,rad}$). These ones in addition to the heat loss by reflection constitute the total heat loss of the receiver (\dot{Q}_{loss}). The four equations describing these physical processes are:

$$\dot{Q}_{solar} = \dot{Q}_{abs} + \dot{Q}_{loss,ref} \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{abs} = \dot{Q}_{cond,wall} + \dot{Q}_{loss,conv} + \dot{Q}_{loss,rad} \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{cond,wall} = \dot{Q}_{conv,HTF} \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{loss} = \dot{Q}_{loss,conv} + \dot{Q}_{loss,rad} + \dot{Q}_{loss,ref} \quad (4)$$

This system of equations is completed with the energy balance applied to the working fluid in each HCE,

$$\dot{Q}_{conv,HTF} = \dot{m} \left[(h_{out} - h_{in}) + \frac{1}{2} (u_{out}^2 - u_{in}^2) \right] \quad (5)$$

where \dot{m} (kg s⁻¹) is the mass flow rate, h is the specific enthalpy (J kg⁻¹)

Table 1
Thermodynamic properties of the state points of supercritical cycle.

State points	P (bar)	T (°C)	h (kJ/kg)
1	267.0	651.30	652.20
2	86.6	510.40	489.90
3	86.0	700.00	721.30
4	85.6	194.10	124.00
5	85.2	78.07	-23.34
6	84.8	35.00	-197.30
7	267.8	73.07	-166.00
8	267.4	189.10	54.89
9	267.4	189.10	54.89
10	267.4	189.10	54.89
Cycle power (MW _e)	50		
Source thermal power (MW _{th})	100.36		
Cycle efficiency (%)	49.82		

and u ($m s^{-1}$) is the velocity. The subscripts in/out refer to the inlet/outlet to/from the control element, respectively. In Eq. (5), the term corresponding to the kinetic energy variation may have a very small contribution with respect to the enthalpy variation, as in the case to be analysed in this work. Nevertheless, it has been included in order to give more generality to the thermal model of the microchannel receiver, so that it can be applied to other thermal fluids and other working conditions. The correlations used to characterise the fluid heating and pressure drop along the flow direction, as well as the heat losses from the receiver are summarised in appendix A.

The second thermal model calculates the temperature at the external surface of the panel, which is necessary to evaluate convective and radiative heat losses. This calculation is performed in a simplified way using a model of network of thermal resistances [26–29]. Although there are many compact structure geometries [22], the simplest case of plain rectangular fin and quadrangular section is considered; in this way, the hydraulic diameter matches one side of the quadrangular wetted perimeter. The model assumes that the channel is surrounded by a continuous conductive solid matrix, and heat is transferred into the fluid from all four surfaces of the channel. Instead of using a fin efficiency term, the model utilises an average sidewall temperature based on conduction resistances as the interface to the fluid temperature node.

Fig. 3 depicts the equivalent thermal circuit in the solar heat flux direction between two consecutive and parallel channels through which the fluid circulates. The heat is transmitted by conduction through the

Table 2
Parameters for the heliostat field calculation.

Design point conditions	
Location (latitude, longitude)	Seville (37.4 N, 5.9 W)
Day and hour	21st June, solar noon
Direct Normal Irradiation, DNI ($W m^{-2}$)	950
Ambient temperature (°C)	25
Effective sky temperature (°C)	15
Wind velocity ($m s^{-1}$)	2
Heliostat geometry and focusing	
Structure width (m) x height (m)	12.2 x 12.2
N. of horizontal panels	2
N. of vertical panels	8
Focusing type	At slant
Optical error parameters	
Elevation pointing error (rad)	0
Azimuth pointing error (rad)	0
Surface slope error in X/Y (mrad)	1.53
Reflected beam error in X/Y (mrad)	0.2
Mirror performance parameters	
Reflective surface ratio	0.97
Mirror reflectivity	0.95
Soiling factor	0.95

plate thickness ($R_{p0,cond}$ in the first plate, $R_{p,cond}$ in an intermediate plate), up to the fin base, where it can be transmitted by convection to the fluid through the channel width ($R_{c,conv}$) or by conduction through the fin length ($R_{f,cond}$); this heat flux can be transmitted by convection from the fin surface to the thermal fluid ($R_{f,conv}$) or by conduction along the entire fin length ($R_{f,cond}$), to be transmitted by convection to the fluid through the channel width ($R_{c,conv}$), or it can be transmitted by conduction through the plate thickness, reinitiating the thermal process again; finally, R_{HTF} is the thermal resistance due to the fluid heat gain. This thermal circuit is repeated, in series, as many times as the number of parallel channel rows ($N_{c,rows}$) along the absorber panel thickness. The mathematical expressions of the previous thermal resistances are given in Ref. [23], where this model is also explained in more detail.

If it is assumed that the absorber panel is symmetrical with respect to the plane at half thickness, because it is irradiated on both sides, the overall thermal resistance should refer to half the thickness, i.e. half of the parallel channel rows. Therefore, this overall resistance ($R_{th,panel}$) is obtained by multiplying the resistance equivalent to one channel by half the number of parallel rows, as in Eq. (6). Here, the symbol || between

Fig. 5. Diagram of the optical process to calculate the optical efficiency and the solar flux maps on the absorber panels.

Table 3

Thermo-fluid dynamic and geometrical parameters of the receiver for the optimisation analysis.

Fixed parameters	Value
Thermal fluid	Supercritical CO ₂
Inlet/Outlet temperature (°C)	510.4/700
Outlet pressure (bar)	86
Material	Inconel 617
Aspect Ratio	0.7
Compact structure	Plain rectangular fin
Channel shape	Quadrangular
Number of channels rows pass 1 & pass 2	6
Design velocity pass 1 (m s ⁻¹)	15
Design velocity pass 2 (m s ⁻¹)	30
Variable parameters	Range
Number of absorber panels	3–8
Panel dimensions (width x height, m x m)	(1.7 x 2.4) - (6.7 x 9.36)
Channel dimensions pass 1 (width x depth, mm x mm)	(6 x 6) - (14 x 14)
Channel dimensions pass 2 (width x depth, mm x mm)	(4 x 4) - (6 x 6)

two terms denotes the harmonic half mean of these terms, which provides the resistance that results from two thermal resistances in parallel; while the thermal resistances in series are simply summed algebraically.

$$R_{th,panel} = R_{p0,cond} + \frac{N_{c,rows}}{2} [R_{p,cond} + \{R_{e,conv} \parallel (R_{f,cond} + ((R_{f,cond} + R_{e,conv}) \parallel R_{f,conv}))\} + R_{HTF}] \quad (6)$$

The equation set to determine each thermal resistance appearing in Eq. (6) is further detailed in appendix B.

The thermo-fluid dynamic model has been validated in Ref. [23], by

comparison with data from a Thermal Resistance Model (TRM) and a Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) model implemented using the Icepak 4.2 software [29]. These models were in turn validated with experimental data obtained from two samples, specifically, 2-layer and 5-layer copper heat sinks [29]. Observations indicate that both the experimental data and simulation results exhibit a similar trend, although the model underestimates the surface temperatures. This discrepancy in the model's accuracy can be attributed to the assumption of uniform wall heat flux for calculating heat transfer coefficients, while also neglecting the solder resistance within the model.

3.2. Thermal and optical boundary conditions for the receiver analysis and receiver sizing

The thermal model is completed with the following boundary conditions: fluid inlet and outlet temperature, fluid inlet pressure, and the required useful thermal power, which refer to the subsystems of the STPP in which the receiver is integrated, namely the solar collection subsystem, the power cycle and the thermal storage. This analysis assumes a solar multiple equal to 1 (i.e., there is no storage, as the plant is supposed to be hybridised with another energy source). Therefore, only the first two subsystems are considered.

Following Gen3 programme recommendations, the power cycle adopted is a supercritical CO₂ (sCO₂) cycle [1]. The main advantage of these cycles regarding other configurations is based on the proximity of the compressor inlet conditions (75–90 bar) to the CO₂ critical point, in which the CO₂ density is high and thus the required compression power is greatly reduced. As a consequence, turbine can use moderate inlet temperatures with no effect on the cycle efficiency [30–33]. It has been selected the recompression-type cycle described by Linares et al. [34]

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig. 6. Thermal properties evolution for the supercritical CO₂ between 500 °C and 700 °C, at 86 bar. (a) Specific heat in J kg⁻¹ K⁻¹; (b) Thermal conductivity in W m⁻¹ K⁻¹; (c) Density in kg m⁻³, and (d) Dynamic viscosity in Pa s (Source: [42]).

Fig. 7. Solving algorithm to design and size a specific microchannel radial receiver..

and depicted in Fig. 4. This cycle is based on the recompression layout, so two compressors are included: the Main Compressor (MC), that supplies the most pressurised stream to the Low Temperature Recuperator (LTR); and the Auxiliary Compressor (AC), that connects to the High Temperature Recuperator (HTR). The main characteristic of this cycle compared to a conventional recompression cycle lies in the position in which the solar thermal power is supplied. This is located downstream the Turbine (T) in the low-pressure side of the cycle where CO_2 pressure is much lower than in a conventional recompression cycle. Besides, the power block considers dry cooling by means of an air-cooled Pre-Cooler (PC).

The net cycle power output has been set to 50 MW_e , which is considered representative of a commercial plant based on this technology [35]. Table 1 shows the thermodynamic properties of the state points following the numbering marked in Fig. 4.

The cycle efficiency is the ratio between the cycle power (\dot{W}_{cycle}) and

the thermal power transferred to the sCO_2 by means of the microchannel solar receiver ($\dot{Q}_{\text{th,receiver}}$), Eq. (7).

$$\eta_{\text{cycle}} = \frac{\dot{W}_{\text{cycle}}}{\dot{Q}_{\text{th,receiver}}} \quad (7)$$

The solar collection subsystem consists of a circular heliostat field, which concentrates the sunlight on the receiver located at the top of the tower. The tower height depends on the thermal power of the receiver, and it is calculated according to state-of-the-art references [36–38]. Once the tower height, thermal power and initial receiver sizing are determined, the heliostat field is computed by means of SolarPilot software [39], considering an external cylindrical receiver with the same height and tower diameter as the corresponding radial receiver of the same thermal power. Then this heliostat field is exported to Soltrace software [40]. Here, the cylindrical receiver is replaced by the

Table 4

Geometrical and thermo-fluid dynamic characteristics of the absorber panel in the optimisation analysis of the number of panels, keeping the panel dimensions and its configuration constant.

Global characteristics of the absorber panel	
Useful thermal power (MW _{th})	12.55
Panel width (m)	3.3
Panel height (m)	4.62
Fluid inlet/outlet temperature (°C)	510.4/700
Total mass flow rate (kg s ⁻¹)	54.18
Pass 1	
Width (m)	1.38
Channel dimensions (mm x mm)	10 x 10
Number of channel rows	6
Intermediate plate thickness (mm)	1
Frontal/back plate thickness (mm)	1.5
Fin thickness/thickness between channels (mm)	3
Average fluid velocity (m s ⁻¹)	15
Mass flow rate per channel (kg s ⁻¹)	0.0821
Average convection heat transfer coefficient (W m ⁻² K ⁻¹)	2.1·10 ³
Pressure drop (bar)	0.475
Pass 2	
Width (m)	1.92
Channel dimensions (mm x mm)	5 x 5
Number of channel rows	6
Plate thickness (mm)	1
Frontal/back plate thickness (mm)	1.5
Thickness between channels (mm)	3
Average fluid velocity (m s ⁻¹)	30
Mass flow rate per channel (kg s ⁻¹)	0.0364
Average convection heat transfer coefficient (W m ⁻² K ⁻¹)	4·10 ³
Pressure drop (bar)	3.6

converging absorber panels before performing the Monte Carlo ray tracing and obtaining the optical efficiency of the solar field as well as the incident flux map on the absorber panel. The ray-tracing methodology consists of the tracing of a specified number of rays from the sun, each of which performs several optical interactions. Some of these interactions are probabilistic in nature, while others are deterministic, such as the analytical calculation of the intersection of a ray with a surface. This code has the advantage of providing accurate results for complex systems that cannot be modelled otherwise. The disadvantage is the longer processing time. Accuracy increases with the number of rays, and more rays means more processing time. In the simulations performed for this work, the number of rays has been equal to 10⁷. Fig. 5 illustrates the optical process by combining SolarPilot and Soltrace to obtain the optical efficiency and concentrated solar flux maps on the receiver panels.

All calculations have been made for nominal conditions of the sCO₂ cycle and design-point conditions of the solar field. This design point conditions, as well as the main parameters of the heliostats, are summarised in Table 2.

A direct coupling between the power cycle and the receiver has been considered, a feature favoured by the pressure of the supercritical CO₂ (85 bar) on the heat supply side. Initially, a pressure drop equal to 0.6 bar is shown in Table 1, as in the rest of the heat exchangers of the power cycle; however, the pressure drop in the solar receiver is considerably higher, as will be seen in section 4.

Table 5

Tower height and optical efficiency as function of the number of panels in the receiver.

Number of panels	Receiver thermal power (MW _{th})	Tower height (m)	η_{opt} (%)	$\eta_{th,rec}$ (%)	$\eta_{ex,rec}$ (%)	$\eta_{th,solar_sub}$ (%)	$\eta_{ex,solar_sub}$ (%)
3	37.64	92.20	74.74	82.89	53.19	61.95	39.75
4	50.18	95.41	78.22	85.88	54.30	67.17	42.47
5	62.73	98.61	79.34	87.70	55.72	69.58	44.20
6	75.27	101.81	79.23	88.89	56.60	70.43	44.85
7	87.82	105.01	78.52	89.63	57.15	70.38	44.87
8	100.36	108.21	77.31	90.18	57.55	69.72	44.49

Fig. 8. Evolution of heat losses from the absorber panel as function of the number of panels, keeping the panel dimensions and its configuration constant.

3.3. Definition of receiver thermal and geometrical parameters and their variation range

The thermal and optical boundary conditions described in the previous section defined several parameters of the microchannel receiver: thermal power; heat transfer fluid, which is supercritical CO₂; inlet and outlet CO₂ temperatures to/from the receiver; and inlet CO₂ pressure to the receiver. Additionally, several parameters referred to the receiver have been set for simplicity in the optimisation analysis: design fluid velocities through each pass of the panel: 15 m s⁻¹ for pass 1 and 30 m s⁻¹ for pass 2; these values have been chosen to ensure proper cooling of the panels, being in the recommended range of pressurised pipeline gas velocities [41]. The Aspect Ratio (AR), which in this case of the radial receiver has been considered equal to the ratio between the receiver height and the tower diameter, and it has been assumed to be 0.7 [10, 36]. The compact structure presents a plain rectangular fin core, with quadrangular channels. In addition, the receiver material is Alloy 617, which is recommended for compact exchangers working at the temperatures at which the solar receiver operates [2], although its main drawback is its low thermal conductivity, around 22.5 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹ [42]. Besides that, the programme warns when any variable falls outside a previously established range. Specifically, it has been established that the external surface temperature of the absorber panel cannot exceed 950 °C, a limitation imposed by the material used; it has also been established that the incident solar flux at the absorber panel can vary between 200 kW m⁻² and 800 kW m⁻². Table 3 presents the fixed and variable parameters of the receiver considered for this optimisation analysis.

The CO₂ thermodynamic properties have been tabulated from NIST database [43] in the working region of the receiver, for temperature steps below 0.4 °C and pressure steps equal to 0.05 bar. Although the working conditions of the CO₂ are supercritical, it is important to note that the thermal properties follow a quasi-linear trend, as the CO₂ is at very high temperature and far away from the critical point. These evolutions are shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 9. Concentrated solar flux map on the absorber panel. (a) Case 3 panels, and (b) Case 8 panels.

Another important issue that should be considered when assessing the results obtained is the possible Heat Transfer Degradation (HTD), mainly due to the high radiation fluxes impinging on the absorber panels [44]. Applying the criteria presented in Ref. [45], it can be concluded that the working conditions of the solar receivers can lead to such degradation. At the moment, as stated in Ref. [44], there are fewer criteria for the onset of HTD in the case of supercritical sCO_2 , so it is difficult to quantify the effect in an analytical model. Experimental work is in progress [46] to reach interesting conclusions on this topic, which is still in an incipient research phase.

3.4. Objective functions for the optimisation analysis and solving algorithm

The first two objective functions are the exergy efficiency and the thermal efficiency of the solar receiver, given by Eq. (8) and Eq. (9), respectively.

$$\eta_{ex,receiver} = \frac{\Delta Ex_{CO_2,receiver}}{\Delta Ex_{solar,receiver}} \quad (8)$$

$$\eta_{th,receiver} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{th,CO_2,receiver}}{\dot{Q}_{solar,receiver}} \quad (9)$$

The exergy efficiency takes into account both thermal losses and fluid pressure drop, and it represents the ratio between the CO_2 exergy increment in the solar receiver and the exergy associated to the solar radiation incident on the absorber surface of the receiver.

As said in section 3.3, the CO_2 in the receiver is far enough from the critical point to assume ideal gas behaviour, so the exergy gain is modelled by Eq. (10) [47], while the exergy associated to the incident solar radiation is calculated by the Parrot Eq. (11) [48].

$$\Delta Ex_{CO_2,receiver} = \dot{m} \left[\Delta h \left(1 - \frac{T_{amb}}{T_{LMTD}} \right) + R T_{amb} \ln \left(\frac{P_{out}}{P_{in}} \right) \right] \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta Ex_{solar} = \dot{Q}_{solar} \left[1 - \frac{4 T_{amb}}{3 T_{sun}} (1 - \cos \delta)^{1/4} + \frac{T_{amb}}{3 T_{sun}} \right] \quad (11)$$

In previous equations, T_{amb} is the ambient temperature; T_{LMTD} is the log mean temperature difference between the HCE outlet and inlet; R is the ideal gas constant; and P is the fluid pressure, evaluated at the inlet

and outlet of the HCE; \dot{Q}_{solar} is the concentrated solar radiation incident on the receiver, also appearing in Eq. (1); T_{sun} is the equivalent temperature of the sun as a blackbody (~ 5800 K); and δ is the half-angle of the cone subtended by the sun's disc ($\delta \sim 4.7$ mrad, on a clear day).

At last, a parametric analysis is achieved by considering the optics of the heliostat field, using an optical efficiency calculated with Soltrace, η_{opt} , and extending the above variables to the entire solar subsystem, Eq. (12) and Eq. (13).

$$\eta_{ex,solar_subsystem} = \eta_{opt} \cdot \eta_{ex,receiver} \quad (12)$$

$$\eta_{th,solar_subsystem} = \eta_{opt} \cdot \eta_{th,receiver} \quad (13)$$

To finish this section, the calculation algorithm to design and size a specific microchannel radial receiver is depicted in Fig. 7. Besides the thermal boundary conditions imposed by the power cycle, there are several geometrical, thermo-fluid or mechanical parameters necessary to define the absorber panel and the receiver. Once the receiver geometry is defined, an average calculation of the main thermo-fluid indicators (Reynolds number, pressure drop) is performed. If the receiver meets these criteria, a second iterative process is started. First, the heliostat field is calculated from the receiver particular design and thermal power, as well as the heliostat field boundary conditions: design point, heliostat geometry and focusing and optical errors. The incident solar flux on the receiver and the optical efficiency are then computed. After that, a more detailed thermo-fluid analysis of the receiver is carried out by applying the two thermal models described in section 3.1. As a result, the fluid heating, pressure drop, and the heat losses from the receiver are calculated. With these values, it is possible to verify whether the initially incident solar flux is enough for the required thermal power, starting the iterative process again if necessary. Once the previous condition is reached, it is accomplished a last calculation of the receiver and the solar sub-system performance, including the thermal and exergy efficiency.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Variation of the number of absorber panels while keeping the panel dimensions and its configuration constant

This subsection analyses the influence of the optical boundary

(a) Evolution of the optical and thermal efficiency, for the receiver and the entire solar subsystem.

(b) Evolution of the optical and exergy efficiency, for the receiver and the entire solar subsystem.

Fig. 10. Evolution of the optical and thermal/exergy efficiency, for the receiver and the entire solar subsystem, as function of the number of panels, keeping the panel dimensions and its configuration constant.

conditions and heat losses on the receiver performance. As an initial condition, an absorber panel with the thermo-fluid dynamic and geometrical characteristics detailed in Table 4 is set. As shown in this table, the dimensions and geometrical characteristics of the absorber panels are kept constant, as well as the CO_2 mass flow rate. As the concentrated solar flux incident on each panel is also kept constant, the thermal power absorbed by the CO_2 circulating through the panel is constant. Under such assumptions, different configurations of radial microchannel receiver have been modelled varying the number of converging absorber panels from 4 (which would provide half of the thermal power required by the sCO_2 cycle, being necessary to install another receiver with similar characteristics or to hybridise with another energy source) to 8 (which would provide 100% the thermal power required by the power cycle, assuming a solar multiple equal to 1 and design-point conditions). The panels are considered to be equidistantly distributed in space, taking as a reference a panel pointing south and the others at equal angles of convergence. It is also assumed that all absorber panels of a particular receiver configuration (number of converging panels and dimensions) have the same irradiance pattern. For all the cases studied, the panel pointing south has been selected as basis to perform the calculations.

It can be calculated from Table 4 that the total CO_2 pressure drop through the two-pass circuit in each absorber panel is approximately equal to 4 bar, and remains constant regardless of the number of panels, since each panel is in parallel with the others. The tower height increases with greater receiver thermal power, as the number of panels increases. This causes the optical efficiency, calculated with Soltrace, to vary, which reaches a maximum value for 5 panels and a tower height equal to 98.6 m, as shown in Table 5.

As can be seen in Fig. 8, the total heat losses decrease with increasing number of converging absorber panels, as the view factor between the panel and the outside is reduced, decreasing the radiation loss. However,

further analysis shows that the heat losses from the panel wall corresponding to flow pass 2, closer to the tower axis, decrease, while the heat losses from the panel wall corresponding to pass 1, closer to the tower circumference, increase. This is because, as the number of converging panels increases, the maximum solar flux on the panel wall is radially displaced from the inner to the outer zone. Fig. 9 shows this different concentrated solar flux map on the absorber panel, obtained by Soltrace, for the case of 3 panels and for the case of 8 panels.

As a conclusion, Fig. 10 shows that the receiver thermal efficiency increases with increasing number of converging panels, because the heat losses decrease. For the same reason, the exergy efficiency increases, as the pressure drop remains constant in this case. However, when applying the optical efficiency, a maximum overall thermal and exergy efficiency results for 7 panels.

4.2. Variation of the channel dimensions for each pass of the panel while keeping the number of panels and the receiver thermal power constant

As indicated in section 2, the proposed receiver presents increasing compactness within the same absorber panel, with the hydraulic diameter of the second pass being smaller than that of the first pass, i.e. the structure becomes more compact as the fluid becomes hotter. In this way, the cooling conditions of the panel are improved, reducing the temperature of the panel external area and thus the heat losses, while at the same time the fluid velocity is adjusted so that the pressure drop does not increase excessively. In this section, the phenomena aforementioned will be quantified numerically.

For this analysis, the absorber panel described in section 4.1, Tables 4 and is used as a reference, considering that it is included in a radial receiver with 4 convergent absorber panels. The following parameters are kept constant: the overall panel dimensions (width and height); the pass width; the plate and fin thicknesses in the compact structure; the number of parallel rows (6 rows in both pass 1 and pass 2); and the total mass flow rate. While the side of the quadrangular channel section is varied: between 8 and 12 mm for pass 1 (channel with the largest hydraulic diameter); and between 4 and 6 mm for pass 2 (channel with the smallest hydraulic diameter). The variation range is small because: for larger hydraulic diameters, the channel thermal resistance is higher, and the temperature of the panel external surface is higher than $950\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; and for smaller hydraulic diameters, the pressure drop is very high. The different channel dimensions result in a variation of the mass flow rate per channel and its velocity. The results obtained are shown in Fig. 11. It shows that heat losses decrease with improved cooling (smaller channel dimensions and higher velocity), while pressure drop follows the opposite trend, increasing with decreasing hydraulic diameter. This different behaviour is not captured in the energy efficiency, whereas it is revealed in the exergy efficiency, which shows a maximum for approximate channel dimensions equal to $(10\text{ mm} \times 10\text{ mm})$ and $(6\text{ mm} \times 6\text{ mm})$, for pass 1 and 2, respectively.

Finally, it is carried out a comparison of the thermal performance of panels of increasing compactness with panels of constant compactness, for which 3 cases of constant hydraulic diameter are evaluated: 4, 5 and 6 mm. Larger channel dimensions have not been considered because it is not possible to guarantee an external surface temperature lower than $950\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for pass 2, and smaller dimensions lead to an excessive pressure drop. Table 6 summarises the cases for constant compactness. It can be observed that the thermal efficiency does exceed the case of increasing compactness for 4 mm, but the pressure drop associated with this configuration is very high, so its exergy efficiency is significantly lower; the maximum exergy efficiency for constant compactness is given for a channel dimension of 6 mm side, and it never exceeds the maximum of increasing compactness.

5. Conclusions

This work aimed at studying and optimising a novel microchannel

Fig. 11°. Different variables as function of the channel dimensions in pass 1 and pass 2 within the same panel. (a) Heat losses; (b) Pressure drop, (c) Thermal efficiency and (d) Exergy efficiency.

Table 6

Heat losses, pressure drop, thermal efficiency and exergy efficiency as function of the channel dimensions in absorber panels of constant compactness.

Pass 1 squared channel width (mm)	Pass 2 squared channel width (mm)	Heat Losses (kW _{th})	Pressure Drop (bar)	Thermal Efficiency (%)	Exergy Efficiency (%)
4	4	989.85	22.56	86.48	49.57
5	5	1019.70	9.50	86.14	53.12
6	6	1052.10	4.78	85.78	54.04

receiver design for pressurised gases and supercritical fluids, which combines two concepts: firstly, the arrangement of the absorber panels, which is radial and converging on the tower axis; secondly, the compact structure presents an increasing compactness with a decreasing hydraulic diameter as the fluid is heated. As a preliminary step to optimisation, boundary conditions have been defined, which are given by the power cycle and the heliostat field. In addition, the geometrical parameters that most influence the performance of the receiver have been selected. Finally, the objective variable function to be maximised has been defined, which in this case is the global exergy efficiency referred to the entire solar subsystem in which the receiver is integrated. The main conclusions of this parametric optimisation analysis are summarised below.

- By increasing the number of absorber panels, keeping the panel dimensions constant, the receiver thermal and exergy efficiency

increase, because heat losses decrease as the view factors from the external panel surface to the outside decrease. However, the optical efficiency of the heliostat field decreases after a certain number of panels, resulting in a maximum exergy efficiency for the entire solar subsystem. For the case analysed in section 4.1, the optimum number of panels is 7.

- The effect of different channel dimensions in each flow pass of the panel is also studied, keeping the panel dimensions and the receiver configuration (number of panels and thermal power) constant. With these assumptions, the optical efficiency is also constant. The heat losses decrease as the channel dimensions are reduced, due to the lower external surface temperature as the heat transfer is enhanced; as a result, the thermal efficiency increases in these conditions. However, the exergy efficiency presents a maximum, as the pressure drop is also balanced. For the case studied in section 4.3, the approximate optimum channel dimensions for passes 1 and 2 are (10 mm × 10 mm) and (6 mm × 6 mm), respectively.
- To demonstrate the advantage of increasing compactness of the panel, compared to constant compactness, the panel with optimised channel dimensions mentioned in the previous conclusion has been compared with panels with constant channel dimensions. As a conclusion, the exergy efficiency is always higher in the increasing compactness panel, since the constant compactness panel with small channels yield to lower heat losses but larger pressure drop; and vice versa, large channels, with lower pressure drop, cause high external panel surface temperature and increase heat losses.

To conclude this section, it is interesting to highlight possible future research lines within the new microchannel receiver presented

in this work, i.e.: analysis of additional compact geometries for the panels of the radial microchannel receiver, maintaining the concept of increasing compactness; study of the coupling to other power cycles and/or with other supercritical or pressurised fluids, to see the effect of changing the boundary conditions; at last, application of this receiver concept to linear Fresnel concentrators, to operate at lower temperatures and generate process heat for industry.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Maria Jose Montes reports financial support was provided by Community of Madrid. Maria Jose Montes reports financial support was provided by Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness. Maria

Jose Montes has patent Receptor solar constituido por paneles absorbedores basados en estructuras compactas issued to 2021/16,158.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A

This appendix contains a more detailed explanation of the equations and correlations used in the thermal model that characterises the thermos-fluid dynamic behaviour of the fluid flowing through the absorber panels and the heat losses from the solar receiver.

A.1. Convection heat transfer to the fluid and pressure drop

The correlations used to characterise the fluid heating and pressure drop along the flow direction are summarised in this section.

Although the work presented in Ref. [23] discusses different correlations, specific to each of the compact geometries included in the comparative analysis, the correlations recommended specifically for sCO₂ in ducts have been adopted for this study [30].

For turbulent flow regime ($Re > 2300$) and straight ducts, Gnielinski correlation is recommended [22,30].

$$Nu_{Dh} = \frac{(f/8) \cdot (Re_{Dh} - 1000) \cdot Pr}{1 + 12.7 \cdot \left(\sqrt{\frac{L}{8}}\right) \cdot (Pr^{2/3} - 1)} \left(\frac{Pr}{Pr_{si}}\right)^{0.11} \quad (A.1)$$

$$f = (1.82 \cdot \log_{10}(Re_{Dh}) - 1.64)^{-2} \quad (A.2)$$

In Gnielinski correlation (Eq. A.1), the friction factor f is calculated as needed from Eq. (A.2); Re_{Dh} is the Reynolds number based on the hydraulic diameter of the duct, D_h ; Pr is the Prandtl number at the fluid temperature; and Pr_{si} is the Prandtl number based on the duct inner surface temperature. These equations are valid up to Reynolds numbers of $5 \cdot 10^6$ and Prandtl numbers ranging from 0.5 to 2000.

It is important to highlight that Eq. (A.1) does not consider entrance effects in the flow by means of the Hausen correction factor: $\left[1 + \left(\frac{d}{L}\right)^{2/3}\right]$. This assumption is valid for the case of solar receivers based on compact structures, where the ratio d/L (hydraulic diameter to length ratio) is negligible, as indicated in Table 4: the hydraulic diameter ranges from 5 mm to 10 mm, while the panel height is 4.62 m.

For laminar flow, it is recommended using $Nu = 4.089$ [22,30]. Since Nusselt number calculated by Gnielinski correlation at $Re_{Dh} = 2300$ is not 4.089, there would be a discontinuity in the evaluation of the Nusselt number. Because of that, a transitional region is defined for Reynolds numbers ranged from 2300 to 5000, where the Nusselt number is evaluated by linear interpolation, according to Eq. (A.3)

$$Nu_{Dh} = 4.089 + \frac{Nu_{Gnielinski}|_{Re=5000} - 4.089}{5000 - 2300} \cdot (Re - 2300) \quad (A.3)$$

In Eq. (A.3), $Nu_{Gnielinski}|_{Re=5000}$ is the Nusselt number calculated by Gnielinski correlation evaluated at a Reynolds number of 5000.

The fluid pressure drop ΔP can be calculated, by means of the Darcy-Weisbach equation evaluated at the averaged values of the fluid in each HCE, Eq. (A.4).

$$\Delta P_{HCE} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot f_D \cdot \left(\frac{L_{HCE}}{D_h}\right) \cdot \rho \cdot u^2 \quad (A.4)$$

In Eq. (A.4), L is the HCE length; D_h is the hydraulic diameter of the duct; ρ is the average fluid density; u is the average fluid velocity; and f_D is the Darcy friction factor, that is four times the Fanning friction factor, f_F : $f_D = 4 \cdot f_F$. This friction factor can be calculated by the following two correlations [22], Eq. (A.5): Hagen-Poiseuille for laminar flow ($Re_{Dh} \leq 2300$), and Techo et al. for turbulent flow ($10^4 \leq Re_{Dh} \leq 10^7$).

$$\begin{cases} f_F = \frac{16}{Re_{Dh}} & \text{for } Re_{Dh} \leq 2300 \\ \frac{1}{f_F} = 1.7372 \cdot \ln \left[\frac{Re_{Dh}}{1.964 \cdot \ln(Re_{Dh}) - 3.8215} \right] & \text{for } 10^4 \leq Re_{Dh} \leq 10^7 \end{cases} \quad (A.5)$$

For the transition region, $2300 < Re_{Dh} < 10^4$, the friction factor is calculated by a linear approximation weighted with the Reynolds number, Eq. (A.6), similar to that already applied to the Nusselt number for transitional flow.

$$f_F = f_{F,2300} + \frac{(f_F|_{Re=10000} - f_F|_{Re=2300}) \cdot (Re - 2300)}{10000 - 2300} \quad (A.6)$$

The local pressure losses due to the fluid distribution between the parallel channels and direction changes are neglected, as the work aims to conclude the general behaviour of the proposed design from a thermo-fluid dynamic and optical point of view. These losses will have to be considered in a more detailed design.

A.2. Heat losses from the receiver

The heat losses from the receiver are described by Eq. (4) in section 3.1. The total heat loss is the sum of the convection, radiation and reflection heat losses.

The convection heat loss is given by Eq. (A.7). This equation is particularised for the external area corresponding to each pass of the absorber panel, each of them characterised by a certain surface temperature.

$$\dot{Q}_{loss,conv} = A_{panel,pass} \cdot h_{conv} \cdot (T_o - T_{amb}) \tag{A.7}$$

In Eq. (A.7), $A_{panel,pass}$ is the external area, corresponding to each pass of the absorber panel, exposed to the ambient; T_o is the external surface temperature; T_{amb} is the ambient temperature; and h_{conv} is the convection heat transfer coefficient between the receiver external surface and the ambient air.

According to Ref. [49], a mixed convection is considered to estimate the effect generated when forced and natural convection act together. This method calculates the mixed convection heat transfer coefficient, \bar{h}_{conv} , by Eq. (A.8).

$$\bar{h}_{conv} = \left(\bar{h}_{fc}^a + \bar{h}_{nc}^a \right)^{1/a} \tag{A.8}$$

In the case of a cavity-type receiver, the recommended value for a is 1.0. The term \bar{h}_{fc} is obtained by estimating the convective heat transfer coefficient for the receiver as if only pure forced convection were occurring, Eq. (A.9). The term \bar{h}_{nc} is obtained by estimating the convective heat transfer coefficient for the receiver as if only pure natural convection were occurring, Eq. (A.10).

$$\bar{h}_{nc} = 0.81 \cdot (T_o - T_{amb})^{0.426} \tag{A.9}$$

$$\bar{h}_{fc} = \frac{k_{air}}{H_{panel}} \left(0.0287 \cdot Re_{air}^{0.8} \cdot Pr_{air}^{1/3} \right) \tag{A.10}$$

In Eq. (A.10), k_{air} is the air thermal conductivity at the film temperature; Re_{air} and Pr_{air} are the Reynolds and the Prandtl numbers for air at the film temperature; finally, H_{panel} is the panel height.

Regarding the radiation and reflection heat losses, the simplified equations Eq. (A.11) and Eq. (A.12) have been used for their estimation.

$$\dot{Q}_{loss,rad} = \sigma \cdot \epsilon_{panel}^f \cdot F_{pass-aperture} \cdot (T_o^4 - T_{amb}^4) \tag{A.11}$$

$$\dot{Q}_{loss,ref} = \left(1 - \epsilon_{panel}^s \right) \cdot F_{pass-aperture} \cdot \dot{Q}_{solar,panel} \tag{A.12}$$

In the previous equations, σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant; ϵ_{panel}^f and ϵ_{panel}^s are the infrared and solar emissivity of the absorber panel external surface; $\dot{Q}_{solar,panel}$ is the concentrated solar radiation incident on the absorber panel; and $F_{pass-aperture}$ is the view factor between the external area corresponding to each pass of the absorber panel, and the aperture. This view factor is calculated applying analytical expressions to the prismatic cavity formed between two converging and consecutive absorber panels.

Appendix B

This appendix describes in more detail each of the thermal resistances that are incorporated in the thermal model that characterises the temperature gradient between parallel channel rows across the absorber panel thickness. The thermal resistance network is shown schematically in Fig. B1.

This analysis by a thermal network is well known and it has been used for cooling of electronic devices [26–28].

Fig. B.1. Scheme of the thermal model that characterises the temperature gradient across the absorber panel thickness, specifying the geometrical parameters of the compact structure.

The expression characterising the equivalent overall thermal resistance is rewritten as a reminder in Eq. (B.1).

$$R_{th,panel} = R_{p0,cond} + \frac{N_{c,rows}}{2} [R_{p,cond} + \{R_{c,conv} \parallel (R_{f,cond} + ((R_{f,cond} + R_{c,conv}) \parallel R_{f,conv}))\}] + R_{HTF} \quad (B.1)$$

$R_{p0,cond}$ and $R_{p,cond}$ are the thermal resistances due to conduction through the wall thickness of the frontal plate, Eq. (B.2), and any intermediate plate of the compact structure, Eq. (B.3), respectively.

$$R_{p0,cond} = \frac{t_{p0}}{k_{rec} \cdot W_{HCE} \cdot L_{HCE}} \quad (B.2)$$

$$R_{p,cond} = \frac{t_p}{k_{rec} \cdot W_{HCE} \cdot L_{HCE}} \quad (B.3)$$

$R_{c,conv}$ is the thermal resistance due to convection between the channel base and top surface, corresponding to the HCE width by length, and the fluid, Eq. (B.4).

$$R_{c,conv} = \frac{1}{h_{conv} \cdot W_{HCE} \cdot L_{HCE}} \quad (B.4)$$

As seen in Fig. B1 and Eq. (B.1), the thermal resistance $R_{c,conv}$ appears twice, corresponding to the convection to the fluid from the channel base and top surface in the heat transfer direction through the absorber panel thickness.

$R_{f,cond}$ is the thermal resistance due to conduction through the fin half length, Eq. (B.5).

$$R_{f,cond} = \frac{\left(\frac{l_f}{2}\right)}{k_{rec} \cdot t_f \cdot L_{HCE}} \quad (B.5)$$

It is noted that the thermal resistance calculated according to Eq. (B.5) corresponds to only half of the total fin length (l_f). This is a simplified way of balancing the decreasing conduction heat transfer along the fin length, because a certain percentage is transferred by convection from the fin to the fluid [29]. As seen in Fig. B1 and Eq. (B.1), this thermal resistance appears twice, combined both in parallel and in series with the thermal resistance due to convection from the fin surface to the fluid, $R_{f,conv}$ (Eq. B.6).

$$R_{f,conv} = \frac{1}{2 \cdot l_f \cdot h_{conv} \cdot L_{HCE}} \quad (B.6)$$

The two in the denominator of Eq. (B.6) refers to the fact that the heat is transferred by convection to the fluid from the surface of two fins, located on both sides of the channel.

Finally, R_{HTF} is the thermal resistance due to the fluid heat gain, defined in Eq. (B.7). This term represents the thermal resistance from the fluid outlet temperature to the fluid inlet temperature. The magnitude of the temperature rise in the fluid depends on the power dissipation and the mass flow rate. Specifically, higher power dissipation or lower mass flow rates result in a larger increase in fluid temperature. Consequently, a higher surface temperature is required to dissipate the same amount of power with the same convection coefficient. This leads to an overall increase in thermal resistance compared to a system where the fluid temperature remains constant.

$$R_{HTF} = \frac{1}{\rho \cdot c_p \cdot u \cdot W_{HCE} \cdot L_{HCE}} \quad (B.7)$$

In previous equations, k_{rec} is the absorber thermal conductivity; h_{conv} is the convection heat transfer coefficient, calculated by Gnielinski correlation (Eq. A.1); ρ , c_p and u are the average fluid density, specific heat and velocity in the HCE; t_{p0} and t_p are the frontal plate and intermediate plate thickness, respectively; l_f and t_f are the fin length and thickness, respectively; and W_{HCE} and L_{CHE} are the HCE width and length, respectively. For clarity, the aforementioned geometrical parameters are also shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. B1.

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